

RI4C2
Research & Innovation
For Cities & Citizens

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101035803

RI4C2 Sessions M18- M24-M30-M36

Report

DELIVERABLE 8.2
MONTH 36

D8.2 – RI4C2 Sessions

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I. Context of the deliverable

A. RI4C2 Sessions

The “Research & Innovation for Cities & Citizens – RI4C2” project aims to extend the activities of the EC2U Alliance to the Research and Innovation fields. The RI4C2 Management Committee (MaCo), the primary governance body, decided to present specific RI4C2 sessions during each EC2U Forum. As presented in the work plan, this session must give a general overview of the project, present the results, and provide key facts and figures on the Partner universities within the Alliance. This session aims to strengthen the links between the two projects and highlight potential collaborations. This present deliverable is a follow-up to D8.1, which presented the RI4C2 sessions from M6 and M12. This deliverable will focus on the RI4C2 Sessions from M18, M24, M30 and M36.

B. Overlap of the dates with the Erasmus + project and the SwafS Project

The EC2U Alliance submitted the SwafS project RI4C2 in 2020, and it is directly linked to the EC2U Erasmus+ project (N°101004065). This Erasmus+ project started on 16th October 2020, i.e., one year before the SwafS project, and ended in October 2023. During this Pilot phase period of the EC2U Alliance, the Fora took place every six months, with a small few-months gap. This means that the M18 RI4C2 Session took place in May 2023 and is included in this deliverable (instead of D8.1 as initially planned). Moreover, the new Erasmus+ project of the EC2U Alliance has started in November 2023, with the Fora now taking place once a year. This has impacted the organisation of the RI4C2 Sessions, as the next Forum of the EC2U Alliance will be organised in October 2024, after the end of the RI4C2 project. Therefore, on top of the M18 and M24 sessions which took place during the EC2U Fora, the M30 and M36 RI4C2 Sessions were organised in the context of two RI4C2 events (RI4C2 Annual meeting in Salamanca, March 2024 and RI4C2 Closing conference in Poitiers, June 2024), to which the whole EC2U community was invited to participate.

C. Key speakers

Prof. Dr. Ludovic Thilly

General Coordinator of the EC2U Alliance, University of Poitiers

Ludovic Thilly is a Full Professor at the University of Poitiers. Since 2012, he has been Executive Vice-Rector in charge of European Networks. A Member of the Executive Board of the Coimbra Group since 2015, he was elected Chair in June 2017 and re-elected in June 2020 and June 2024 for four years. He is also the Chairman of the Executive Board of Coimbra Group. Ludovic Thilly is a Physicist and works on the deformation mechanisms of (nano-)materials. He has co-authored 70+ publications in international peer-reviewed journals (incl. 4 book chapters) and given 50+ invited lectures at international conferences and institutions. Professor Thilly is the Coordinator of the EC2U European University Alliance and coordinates the informal group of the 24 newly selected Alliances.

Ricardo Costa, University of Salamanca
Strategy and Impact Expert

Ricardo, a developmental biologist and research manager, currently leads the "Unidad de Producción Agrícola y Medioambiente" project at CIALE Institute. With a Ph.D. from the University of Cambridge and expertise in embryonic development, he co-established the Healing Foundation Research Centre. Combining scientific and business acumen, he contributed to nanobiology ventures and excelled in technology transfer at VIB Ghent. Trained in management at Instituto de Empresa, he established a tech transfer office at CRAG under the Severo Ochoa award. Certified in strategic innovation, he manages AGRIENVIRONMENT, a RIS3 policy project in Salamanca. Ricardo is an RTTP candidate and an associate consultant for Oxentia. Engaged in EC2U Erasmus+, he connects RI4C2 H2020 with the European University Alliance.

Dana Strauss, University of Jena
Head of office of the regional network JenaVersum

Dana Strauss works as the head of office of the regional network JenaVersum at the University of Jena. She is responsible for coordinating the collaborative platform in order to strengthen the dialogue between research institutions, the city, and businesses. Dana received her doctoral degree in social geography.

Ionel Mangalagiu, Alexandru Ioan Cuza University of Iași
Professor of organic and medicinal chemistry

Dr. Mangalagiu is a professor of organic and medicinal chemistry and Vice-Rector for research at Alexandru Ioan Cuza University of Iași, Romania. He has nearly 30 years of research experience in Heterocyclic Compounds and has published over 150 papers, 15 patents, and 3 international book chapters. He has held various academic positions, including Dean and Head of the Organic Chemistry Department, as well as Vice-Rector for Research. Dr. Mangalagiu has been a visiting professor and invited speaker at prestigious universities such as Ludwig Maximilian University Munchen and Université Paris Sud. His numerous awards include the DAAD and NATO awards, "Costin D. Nenitescu Medal," "Al.I.Cuza University Award in Research," and the "Grand Prize Euroinvent."

Daniela Ovardia, University of Pavia
Co-director Neuroscience and Society Lab

Daniela Ovardia is a science journalist, neuroscientist, and neuroethicist at the University of Pavia. She studied medicine and neuroscience at Università Statale in Milan, Italy, and neuroethics at the University of Pennsylvania in Philadelphia, US. She serves as the Co-director of the Neuroscience and Society Lab at the University of Pavia and is also the Scientific Director of Agenzia Zoe, an agency specialising in science journalism and writing. Furthermore, she is a professor for doctoral students in 'Ethics of Research and Responsible Research and Innovation' and for undergraduate students in Psychology, teaching 'Neuroethics' and 'Communication of Neuroscience' at the University of Pavia in Italy.

Matthias Piontek, University of Jena
Technology Transfer Expert

Matthias Piontek has more than 20 years of experience in Business Administration (M.Sc. in BA - University of Jena and Master of Business and Engineering - Steinbeis University Berlin), worked several years for a start-up before going back into academia. He did research in the fields of Entrepreneurship, Innovation Ecosystems and Start-ups. Since 2014, he uses his previous experiences to support founder as a start-up coach and also manages a network of universities founder services in the federal State of Thuringia. As a two-time Erasmus-Alumni and participant of an international Master programme, he is a strong advocate of the European Idea.

Ana Santos Carvalho
Science Communication coordinator

Ana Santos Carvalho, PharmD, PhD, is the Science Communication Coordinator at Institute of Interdisciplinary Research (iiiUC) from University of Coimbra (UC). She is responsible for European Researchers' Night at Coimbra, Three Minute Thesis Competition (UC 3MT) and SoapBox Science Coimbra. She collaborates in training and supporting initiatives such as the UC Doctoral Schools, Initiative for Promotion of Scientific Culture, Research Seed Awards, among others. She is an invited assistant professor at the Faculty of Pharmacy and Faculty of Psychology and Education Sciences, UC. She is the President of SciComPt, the Portuguese Association of Science Communication. She is member of the Citizen Science Network in Portugal CC.pt, and member of the board of the Portuguese Association of Women Scientists, AMONET.

Bettina Böhm
Research Assistant

Bettina Böhm graduated in physical geography from the University of Munich, Germany, in 1992 and specialised in geoscientific remote sensing. Until 1996, she was a research associate at the German Aerospace Centre in Oberpfaffenhofen, Germany. Since 1997, she has been a research assistant at the Institute of Geography at the Friedrich Schiller University in Jena. Since 2010, she has been involved as a research coordinator in the establishment and expansion of innovative R&D networks with partners in the European and in the Asia-Pacific regions. Since February 2021, she has been working in the EC2U Alliance and coordinates the activities at the University of Jena in WP6, Sustainable Cities and Communities.

Dr. Claudia Hillinger
Head of International Office

Claudia Hillinger is currently the Head of the International Office at the University of Jena and the Career Service. In addition, she is co-leading the activities of the University of Jena in EC2U and RI4C2.

Marion Albouy
Public Health professor and medical doctor

Marion Albouy is a Professor of Public Health at the University of Poitiers, specialising in environmental health promotion. As a doctor at the university hospital of Poitiers, she leads the public health department overseeing therapeutic patient education, health promotion, risk management, ecologic transition, epidemiology, and sexual health. Marion is also involved in the health promotion platform "La Vie la Santé," employing a salutogenic intervention model house. Her collaborative research covers social psychology, physical activity science, biostatistics, toxicokinetics, analytical chemistry, sociology, and economics. Marion's work focuses on developing personal skills and favourable environments to address health inequalities and explores the relationship between prenatal exposure to endocrine disruptors and infant development. She introduces the concept of the psycho-exposome, emphasising the impact of social and behavioural factors on environmental health.

Pauline Bordiec
Project Manager

Pauline Bordiec is currently the RI4C2 Project Manager. She holds a Master's degree in English studies, and she has specialised in international relations and project management. As the project manager, Pauline coordinates all RI4C2 activities and liaises with stakeholders involved in the project. She oversees the correct implementation of the activities and objectives of the project, ensuring to connect all the actors of its ecosystem (decision-makers, researchers, companies, citizens, etc).

Soile Haverinen
Head of Development

Soile Haverinen is the Head of Development responsible for developing and furthering EU advocacy and multidisciplinary research issues at the Research Services of the University of Turku. Her longstanding experience in research management and leadership includes both national and international research funding, as well as other research management issues. Soile has notably been working with EU Research and Innovation Framework Programmes since FP3, and actively engaged in the Finnish Association of Research Managers and Advisors, Finn-ARMA, since its start.

Lenuta Alboaie
Professor

Lenuta Alboaie is a Professor at the Faculty of Computer Science, Alexandru Ioan Cuza University of Iași. For the past fifteen years, she has connected academia and industry through various scientific events, research projects, and entrepreneurial initiatives. She has served as Director of the Computer Science Doctoral School since 2020, Founder and Director of Technological Transfer Center - iTransfer since 2019, and Vice-Dean from 2013 to 2020. Her research in distributed systems, trust and reputation in social networks, and semantic Web has led to over 70 publications and participation in 18 research projects. She is a strong advocate for Women in STEM, co-founding WITChIS, and representing Romania in the IVLP program "Empowering Women in STEM - Hidden No More."

Ana Iolanda VODA
Lecturer in Economics and Business Administration

Ana Iolanda Voda is a Lecturer at the Faculty of Economics and Business Administration, Alexandru Ioan Cuza University of Iasi, Romania, habilitated starting with 2021 in the field of Business Administration, and holds a Ph.D., in Economics since 2011. With nearly 12 years of experience in research she has served as director or management committee representative for 10 national or international projects funded through the Romanian Ministry of Education, Erasmus +, H2020 or COST. She has published over 34 articles indexed in Web of Science, attended over 50 conferences worldwide, received 15 awards for her papers published and has a H-index of 15. Within RI4C2, she is the Local Coordinator for WP6 (UAIC).

Rita Martins dos Santos
Project Manager

Rita is the Local Coordinator of the RI4C2 Project and worked at the University of Coimbra between 2019 and 2023. She has always been involved in Science Management and Communication projects. She is a PhD student in Governance, Knowledge and Innovation at the Faculty of Economics of the University of Coimbra. She recently embarked on a new adventure and took on a new project in the private sector as a Continuous Improvement Project Manager.

Bart Veys

Head of the Policy Unit of the Cost Association

Bart is currently the Head of the Policy Unit at the COST Association. He joined COST in 2016 as a Policy Officer, focusing on European research and innovation policies, stakeholder engagement, and strategy development. From 2014 to 2016, he served as an EU Affairs Advisor at Eindhoven University of Technology in the Netherlands. Prior to that, he held positions at the UNESCO EU Office in Brussels and the Belgian Ministry of Foreign Affairs. He holds Master of Science degrees in International Relations and Economics from Ghent University and in European Studies from the College of Europe.

Tilman Turpin

Programme Coordinator UP-SQUARED / Impact-UP

Tilman Turpin joined the University of Poitiers (UP) in May 2023 as the programme coordinator for two transformative initiatives. UP-SQUARED is a ten-year, government-funded programme aimed at transforming UP into a sustainable university through interdisciplinary research and strengthening the link between education, research, innovation, and scientific culture. Before joining UP, Tilman was a senior advisor at the Institute of Advanced Studies in Education and Training, overseeing research and training for high-level university staff. He has also held management positions at Sciences Po Paris, including campus director in Poitiers and Reims. Tilman holds a PhD in Political Science from Sciences Po Paris and teaches political science and political theory.

II. RI4C2 Session - EC2U Forum N°6 Jena (Germany)

A. Agenda of the RI4C2 Session

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RI4C2 session in Jena EC2U Forum

“Connecting the Dots - Sustainable and Innovative Research Collaborations across Disciplines, Universities and Cities”

EC2U Forum, Jena, Germany

Thursday 25th May 2023
11.30am - 13.00 pm CET

11.30am – 11.40am CET: Introduction to RI4C2 project for Research and Innovation Capacity Building within the EC2U Alliance, Ludovic Thilly (EC2U Coordinator General and RI4C2 Coordinator)

11.40am – 12.20pm CET: Round table #1. Connecting Vision & Institutions
Moderator: Ludovic Thilly (EC2U Coordinator General and RI4C2 Coordinator)

Speakers (7 minutes each):

- **Ricardo Costa** (Strategy and Impact Expert, Vice Rectorate for Research and Knowledge Transfer of the University of Salamanca), “Salamanca network of innovation”;
- **Dana Strauss** (RI4C2 WP5 Leader & Managing Director of Jena Versum at the University of Jena), “JenaVersum Policy”;
- **Ionel Mangalagiu** (Vice-Rector for Research at the University of Alexandru Ioan Cuza in Iasi), “UAIC Policy in the field of innovation with local ecosystem”;
- **Q&As** (incl. online questions from Woodlap).

12.20pm – 12.45pm CET: Round table #2. Connecting People & Actions
Moderator: Dana Strauss (RI4C2 WP5 Leader & Managing Director of JenaVersum at the University of Jena)

Speakers (7 minutes each):

- **Daniela Ovidia** (RI4C2 WP7 Leader, University of Pavia), “Third mission and knowledge sharing: the role of universities and research centres in building the scientific citizenship”;

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- **Matthias Piontek** (Technology Transfer Expert at the University of Jena), "Orchestrating Regional Knowledge Exchange: Finding the Right Players and Balancing KPIs for an Open Dialogue";
- **Q&As** (incl. online questions from Wooclap)

12.45 pm -12.55pm CET: RI4C2 Poster pitches & Conclusion
Moderator: Ludovic Thilly (EC2U Coordinator General and RI4C2 Coordinator)

Speakers:
RI4C2 WP1 Carolina Lioré
RI4C2 WP2 Jorge Hernandez
RI4C2 WP3 Nina Muzykantova
RI4C2 WP4 Gaia Garancini
RI4C2 WP5 Eleonore Roderfeld
RI4C2 WP6 Daniela Soitu
RI4C2 WP7 Pauline Bordiec
RI4C2 WP8 Ludovic Thilly
Conclusion Ludovic Thilly

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B. Speakers

The first roundtable was moderated by Ludovic Thilly, and the session included the following list of speakers:

- **Ricardo Costa** (University of Salamanca)
Strategy and Impact Expert, Vice Rectorate for Research & Knowledge Transfer
- **Dana Strauss** (University of Jena)
RI4C2 WP Leader & Managing Director of JenaVersum
- **Ionel Mangalagiu** (Alexandru Ioan Cuza University of Iasi)
Vice-Rector for Research

The second roundtable was moderated by Dana Strauss, and the session included the following list of speakers:

- **Daniela Ovidia** (University of Pavia)
RI4C2 WP4 Leader
- **Matthias Piontek** (University of Jena)
Technology Transfer Expert

C. Description of the session

This session took place from 11:30am to 13:00pm on Thursday 25th of May, 2023 at the University of Jena and was livestreamed on the EC2U YouTube channel. This session was organised during the EC2U Forum, to promote the activities of the “Research & Innovation for Cities & Citizens – RI4C2” project and foster connections with all the actors involved in the EC2U Alliance as a whole. The goal of the session, named “Connecting the Dots – Sustainable and Innovative Research Collaborations across Disciplines, Universities and Cities”, was to showcase the links created between different stakeholders across the Alliance. Thus, the session was divided into two roundtables.

The first roundtable focused on “Connecting Vision & Institution”, and focused on institutional policies and strategies to foster collaborations among different types of stakeholders within the university ecosystem and its network of innovators. This first roundtable thus presented a more global and strategic vision on the topic.

The second roundtable focused on “Connecting People & Actions”, providing concrete examples on how to connect different stakeholders and citizens to participate in scientific activities. The two presentations showcased good practices on how to connect different actors to facilitate the exchange of good practices and develop cross-sectoral collaborations.

Both roundtables were followed by a Q&As session, encouraging discussions between the different actors of the EC2U community and RI4C2 project on the topic.

As the goal of the RI4C2 project is also to showcase its activities and results, a poster session followed the two roundtables, where the audience could read about RI4C2 outputs while discussing the activities with the RI4C2 team and representatives of each Work Package. Indeed, there was one poster per Work Package, allowing all of the activities of the project to be highlighted in order to foster discussions on all aspects of the project.

Figure 1: End of the RI4C2 Session – Q&A I

Figure 2: Presentation of the posters before the poster session

Figure 3: Example of a poster displayed during the RI4C2 Session at the EC2U Forum in Jena

D. Dissemination of the session

1. Visual used on social media

Figure 4: promotion visual used by Jena University

2. Graphic recording of the session

Figure 5: Graphic recording by Blanche Illustrates

3. Video on the EC2U YouTube channel

This session is available on the [EC2U YouTube channel](#).

III. RI4C2 Session - EC2U Forum N°7 Poitiers (France)

A. Agenda of the RI4C2 Session

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RI4C2 session
“Advancing Together: Citizen Science in Action”

EC2U Forum, Poitiers, France

Thursday 19th October 2023
11.00am - 12.30 pm CET

Moderator: Ricardo Costa, University of Salamanca

11.00am – 11.05am CET: Introduction to the session
Ludovic Thilly (EC2U Coordinator General and RI4C2 Coordinator)

11.05am – 11.20am CET: All aboard for Citizen Science

- *Ana Santos Carvalho (Science Communication Coordinator, University of Coimbra)*

11.20am – 11.25am CET: Q&As

11.25am – 11.40am CET: Public health intervention research: 2 examples of collaborative science in healthy home habits

- *Marion Albouy (Public Health professor and medical doctor, University of Poitiers)*

11.40am – 11.45am CET: Q&As

11.45am - 12.00pm CET: EC2U School Research Projects – Connecting the EC2U Virtual Institutes with local schools

- *Claudia Hillinger (Head of the International Office, University of Jena)*
- *Bettina Böhm (Research Associate in Geoinformation Science, University of Jena)*

12.00pm – 12.05pm CET: Q&As

12.05pm – 12.10pm CET: Presentation of the Living Labs for Citizen Science conference

- *Daniela Soitu (WP6 Leader, University of Iasi)*

12.10pm – 12.20pm CET: Invitation to the Makeathon

- *Dana Strauß (WP5 Leader, University of Jena)*

12.20pm – 12.30pm CET: interactive discussion with the audience

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101035803

B. Speakers

This session was moderated by Ricardo Costa (University of Salamanca) and included the following speakers:

- **Ludovic Thilly** (University of Poitiers)
EC2U Coordinator General and RI4C2 Coordinator
- **Ana Santos Carvalho** (University of Coimbra)
Science Communication Coordinator
- **Bettina Böhm** (University of Jena)
Research Associate in Geoinformation Science
- **Claudia Hillinger** (University of Jena)
Head of International Office
- **Marion Albouy** (University of Poitiers)
Public Health professor and medical doctor
- **Daniela Soitu** (University of Iasi)
RI4C2 WP6 Leader
- **Dana Strauss** (University of Jena)
RI4C2 WP5 Leader

C. Description of the session

This session focused on the H2020 project of the EC2U Alliance: "Research and Innovation for Cities and Citizens – RI4C2", the goal of which is to expand the Alliance's joint future-oriented activities to the Research and Innovation dimension.

This session particularly focused on the Citizen Science activities conducted either within partner universities or within the EC2U Alliance, in a session called "Advancing Together: Citizen Science in Action". 3 different projects from 3 partner universities (Universities of Coimbra, Poitiers and Jena) were presented. Two major ongoing or upcoming activities of the RI4C2 project were then presented: the creation of the Living Labs and the organisation of a Makeathon event to foster innovation and co-creation. The session was made interactive with a Padlet to collect questions and reactions from the audience and launch discussions.

Figure 6: RI4C2 Session in Poitiers

D. Dissemination of the session

1. Visual used on social media

Figure 7: Visual used to promote the RI4C2 Session

2. Video on the EC2U YouTube channel

This session is available on the [EC2U YouTube channel](#).

IV. RI4C2 Session – RI4C2 Annual meeting, Salamanca (Spain)

A. Agenda of the RI4C2 session

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Day 2 | 13th March

RI4C2 Session: "Beyond RI4C2"

9:00h – 10:30h | **1. Funding: Investment pathway on the EC2U research & innovation landscape**

- 1.1 **R&I dimension of alliances**
 - *Prof. Dr. Ludovic Thilly, Coordinator General of the EC2U Alliance.*
 - *Joerg Niehoff, Deputy Head of Unit ERA Governance and Implementation European Commission, DG Research & Innovation.*
- 1.2 **Overview of EU work programmes**
 - *Ursula Castro, Head of Policy and Comms. Department, COST Association - European Cooperation in Science and Technology.*

10:30h – 12.00h | **2. Engagement: Connecting researchers**

- 2.1 **Digital Environment**
 - *Prof. Dr. Daniela Ovadia, University of Pavia*
- 2.2 **Developing common research proposals**
 - *Dr. Tilman Turpin, University of Poitiers*

12.00h – 12.30h | *Coffee Break*

12.30h – 14.00h | **3. Ecosystem: RI4C2 connections to EC2U**

- 3.1 **Inter-alliance Living Labs conference.**
 - *Prof. Dr. Fernando Almaraz, University of Salamanca*
- 3.2 **Open science policies**
 - *Prof. Dr. Alboaie Lenuta & Prof. Dr. Ionel Mangalagiu, UAIC-University of Iasi*
 - *Laura Niemi, University of Turku*
- 3.3 **Launch of the PEKE**
 - *Pauline Bordieac, University of Poitiers*

UNIVERSIDADE DE COIMBRA

UNIVERSITATEA „ALEXANDRU IOAN CUZA” din IASI

FRIEDRICH-SCHILLER-UNIVERSITÄT JENA

UNIVERSITÀ DI PAVIA

Université de Poitiers

UNIVERSIDAD DE SALAMANCA

TURUN YLIOPISTO

B. Speakers

This session was moderated by Ricardo Costa (University of Salamanca) and included the following speakers:

- **Prof. Dr. Ludovic Thilly** (University of Poitiers)
General Coordinator of the EC2U Alliance
- **Ionel Mangalagiu** (Alexandru Ioan Cuza University of Iasi)
Professor
- **Bart Veys**
Head of the Policy Unit of the Cost Association
- **Fernando Almaraz** (University of Salamanca)
Coordinator of ENIHEI, European Network of Innovative Higher Education Institutions
- **Prof. PhD Lenuta Alboaic** (Alexandru Ioan Cuza University of Iasi)
Director of the Doctoral School, Faculty of Computer Science and Director of iTransfer Technological Transfer Center
- **Daniela Ovidia** (University of Pavia)
Co-director Neuroscience and Society Lab
- **Tilman Turpin** (University of Poitiers)
PhD Programme Coordinator UP-SQUARED/ Impact-UP
- **Joerg Niehoff**
Deputy Head of Unit for “ERA, Spreading Excellence and Research Careers” in DG Research & Innovation
- **Laura Niemi** (University of Turku)
D.Sc. (Econ. & Bus. Adm.)
- **Pauline Bordiec** (University of Poitiers)
RI4C2 Project Manager

C. Description of the session

The RI4C2 session in Salamanca, named “Beyond RI4C2,” explored the future of the EC2U research and innovation landscape with the RI4C2 legacy. The session focused on strategic funding pathways, researcher engagement, and strengthening ecosystem connections within the EC2U network.

Key discussions included insights into the Connect EU initiative and EU work programmes, highlighting opportunities for future projects and collaborations. The importance of engaging researchers was

emphasised through discussions on the digital environment for research and the development of common research proposals, showcasing the benefits of collaborative efforts across institutions.

The session also highlighted the RI4C2 project's strong connections to the EC2U ecosystem, with presentations on the inter-alliance “Living Labs conference” and Open Science policies, underlining a commitment to open and accessible research. The upcoming launch of the PEKE event was also presented, highlighting the project's achievements and future goals.

Overall, the session demonstrated how the RI4C2 project is strengthening the EC2U Alliance through strategic funding, active researcher engagement, and ecosystem integration.

D. Dissemination of the session

1. Visual used on social media

Figure 8: Visual of the event used to promote the RI4C2 Session

2. Video on the EC2U Youtube Channel

This session is available on the EC2U YouTube Channel:

[RI4C2 Session in Salamanca Part 1](#)

[Part 2 Session in Salamanca Part 2](#)

[Part 3 Session in Salamanca Part 3](#)

V. RI4C2 Session – RI4C2 closing conference, Poitiers (France)

A. Agenda of the RI4C2 session

Wednesday 12 th June 9:00 – 18:30 CET	
9:00 – 12:15	RI4C2 Session – Connecting people and talents: building a sustainable network
9:00 – 9:15	Introductory remarks <ul style="list-style-type: none">- Tilman Turpin, <i>University of Poitiers</i>
9:15 – 10:15	Connecting people <ul style="list-style-type: none">- "Innovation through Collaboration", Dana Strauß, <i>Head of regional network JenaVersum, University of Jena</i>- "Community Engagement and the First Citizen Science Initiatives", Iolanda Voda, <i>Lecturer Ph.D. Habil., Faculty of Economics and Business Administration, University of Iași</i>
10:15 – 10:45	Coffee Break
10:45 – 11:45	Empowering talents <ul style="list-style-type: none">- "Mainstreaming Open Science", Soile Haverinen, <i>Head of Development, Research Services, University of Turku</i>- "Empowering Careers through the EC2U Alliance", Rita Martins dos Santos, <i>Project Manager, University of Coimbra</i>
11:45 – 12:00	Concluding remarks <ul style="list-style-type: none">- Tilman Turpin, <i>University of Poitiers</i>

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B. Speakers

This session was moderated by Tilman Turpin, PhD Programme Coordinator UP-SQUARED/ Impact-UP at the University of Poitiers, and included the following speakers:

- **Dana Strauss** (University of Jena)
Head of the JenaVersum network
- **Ana Iolanda Voda** (Alexandru Ioan Cuza University of Iasi)
RI4C2 WP6 Local Coordinator
- **Soile Haverinen** (University of Turku)
Head of Development, Research Services
- **Rita Martins dos Santos** (University of Coimbra)
Project Manager

C. Description of the session

The RI4C2 session aimed to promote the project's activities, network, and connect with the EC2U E+ project. The event focused on launching the PEKE by building a network of stakeholders and talents under the theme "Connecting people and talents: building a sustainable network".

Moderated by Tilman Turpin from the University of Poitiers, the session featured discussions on Connecting People and Empowering Talents. Dana Strauss from the University of Jena discussed "Innovation through Collaboration," highlighting WP5's sustainable network and the Recipes of Innovation publication. Iolanda Voda from the University of Iasi presented "Community Engagement and the First Citizen Science Projects," emphasising pilot Living Labs and Citizen Science projects. In the segment on Empowering Talents, Soile Haverinen from the University of Turku talked about "Mainstreaming Open Science," focusing on policies nurturing Open Science activities within RI4C2 and the EC2U Open Science community. Rita Martins dos Santos from the University of Coimbra presented "Empowering careers through the EC2U Alliance," showcasing initiatives for Gender Equality, researcher mobility, and institutional HRS4R label efforts.

Overall, the session highlighted how the 3-year RI4C2 project strengthened the EC2U Alliance by integrating diverse stakeholders and providing tools for skill development within the EC2U Community.

D. Dissemination of the session

1. Visual used on social media

Figure 9: Visual of the event used to promote the RI4C2 Session

2. Video on the EC2U Youtube Channel

The RI4C2 Session is available on the EC2U YouTube channel:

[RI4C2 Session in Poitiers – part 1](#)

[RI4C2 Session in Poitiers – part 2](#)

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